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A Study of the Decomposition Patterns of Some Transition Metal Complexes Derived mainly from the Heterocyclic Ligands viz., Furan-2-carboxaldoxime and 3-Methyl-4-arylazopyrazole-5-one using Thermogravimetric Analysis

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AMONG the methods finding extensive use in characterisation of transition metal complexes, TGA is one of the most recent methods. Besides indicating the presence of coordinating groups in a complex molecule, it describes in detail the decomposition pattern for the complex. In the present paper the TGA data in the temperature range 20-800° of some complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) containing either of the two title ligands along with one or more water molecules and an heterocyclic amine or diamine, are described.

Experimental

The two types of complexes used in the study are derived from either the neutral or the anionic form of antifuran-2-carboxaldoxime or 3-methyl-4-(*p*-methylphenylazo)pyrazole-5-one as primary ligand and water, pyridine (py), picoline (pic), aniline (an), ethylenediamine (en), propylenediamine (pn), 2-2'-bipyridyl (bipy) or *o*-phenanthroline (phen) as secondary ligand. The preparation and characterisation of the complexes were reported in a previous communication¹⁻³. The Cu(II) complexes were assigned planar and Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes octahedral structure, respectively.

Results and Discussion

Complexes derived from antifuran-2-carboxaldoxime: The various complexes which have been subjected to TGA study are of the type [Co or Ni(FDH)₂dam]Cl₂; [Co(FDH)₂](NO₃)₂; [Ni(FD)₂dam] where FDH and FD refer to the neutral and the anionic form of the oxime and dam stands for ethylenediamine (en), propylenediamine (pn), 2-2'-bipyridyl (bipy) or *o*-phenanthroline (phen)¹⁻³. The general decomposition pattern of some of the complexes of different categories is as given below.

It appears from the above equations that in most of the complexes a slight decomposition

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begins at 80 or 100° and continues up to 120° and corresponds to the loss of water. This is the range in which the lattice water is lost and hence these water molecules are not coordinated as indicated in the formulae of complexes. No decomposition occurs between 120-180°. The two chloride ions are lost between 180-200°. From 220° to 280° there is a very sharp decrease in weight due to the loss of oxime and different amines. The complex is

changed to the simple metal oxide above 500° and the curve then becomes a straight line.

Complexes derived from 3-methyl-4-(p-methylphenylazo)pyrazole-5-one: The TGA studies of the free azo compound (PyrH C₁₁H₁₁N₄O), its two complexes with Cu(II) and Ni(II) sulphates, free Cu(II) and Ni(II)-3-methyl-4-(p-methylphenylazo)-5-pyrazolonates [M(C₁₁H₁₁N₄O)₂] and their complexes^{4,5} with different amines are described in the following equations.

It appears from the above equations that the lattice water is lost between 80-120°, while the coordinated water is lost at slightly higher temperature around 280°. The coordinated amine usually decomposes in the range 140-200°, the individual temperature, however, varies with the nature of amine and complex. The azo groups are lost completely around 380° and thereafter, the formation of the metal oxide occurs and no decomposition takes place upto 1000°.

References

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Zinc(II) with Dibasic Acids and Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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As a part of the programme on d¹⁰ metal complexes, some penta-coordinated zinc(II) complexes with nitrogen and sulphur donor ligands were reported¹⁻³ earlier from this laboratory. More recently Sharma and Jain reported⁴ some mixed ligand complexes of nickel(II) with dibasic acids and primary and heterocyclic amines as secondary ligands. This communication reports some penta-coordinated mixed ligand complexes of zinc(II) succinate, malonate, glutarate or adipate with

thiocyanate and nitrogen donor ligands like α -picoline and morpholine.

Experimental

Ethanollic solutions of zinc chloride, the organic acid and potassium thiocyanate were mixed in stoichiometric ratio and filtered directly into an ethanollic solution of α -picoline or morpholine. The resulting precipitate was suction filtered, washed with ethanol and ether, recrystallised from carbon tetrachloride/methanol and dried *in vacuo*.

Zinc, thiocyanate and nitrogen were estimated by standard methods. Carbon and hydrogen were microanalysed. The conductance measurements were carried out on 10⁻³ M solutions in pyridine using Toshniwal conductivity bridge, type CL 0102, with a dip type cell. Infrared spectra were recorded in the region 4000-400 cm⁻¹ by Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. Thermogravimetric studies⁵ were carried out in a manually operated thermobalance. Analytical and physical data for the complexes are recorded in Table 1.

As the α -picoline complexes take up moisture and decompose due to hydrolysis, these were kept in a desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Results and Discussion

The molar conductance values (Table 1) of all the compounds indicate them to be 1 : 1 electrolytes. In the ir spectra, the stretching bands due to C=O of malonic, succinic, glutaric and adipic acids at 1724, 1730, 1695 and 1700 cm⁻¹, respectively have been lowered to 1630, 1635, 1630 and 1610 cm⁻¹ in the corresponding complexes indicating the coordination of acids through carboxylate oxygen⁶. The bands appearing at 2050-2080 and 785-860 cm⁻¹ due to ν (C-N) and ν (C-S), respectively indicate the presence of N-bonded thiocyanate group⁶. The bands at ~3210 and ~1115 cm⁻¹, due to

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF MIXED LIGAND ZINC(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	m.p. °C	%Zn	%thio- cyanate	%N	%C	%H	Δ_M mhos [#]
K[Zn(α -pic)M.H ₂ O(NCS)]	210(d)	17.23 (17.41)*	15.2 (15.45)	7.55 (7.41)	31.81 (31.78)	3.01 (2.98)	66
K[Zn(α -pic)S.H ₂ O(NCS)]	200(d)	16.52 (16.79)	14.76 (14.89)	7.00 (7.17)	33.67 (33.88)	3.42 (3.36)	68
K[Zn(α -pic)G.H ₂ O(NCS)]	230(d)	16.02 (16.20)	14.27 (14.37)	6.78 (6.90)	35.34 (35.51)	3.90 (3.72)	74
K[Zn(α -pic)A.H ₂ O(NCS)]	250(d)	15.41 (15.65)	13.76 (13.90)	6.42 (6.67)	37.00 (37.18)	3.8 (4.0)	70
K[Zn(moph)M.H ₂ O(NCS)]	112	17.42 (17.69)	15.58 (15.73)	7.67 (7.57)	26.74 (26.98)	3.62 (3.54)	71
K[Zn(moph)S.H ₂ O(NCS)]	105	16.88 (17.05)	15.01 (15.12)	7.22 (7.30)	27.98 (28.16)	4.08 (3.94)	69
K[Zn(moph)G.H ₂ O(NCS)]	138	16.27 (16.45)	14.51 (14.60)	6.86 (7.04)	30.00 (30.19)	4.50 (4.31)	78
K[Zn(moph)A.H ₂ O(NCS)]	172	15.66 (15.89)	14.00 (14.10)	6.57 (6.80)	31.84 (32.08)	4.74 (4.65)	75

*Figures in parentheses indicate calculated values. M=malonate, S=succinate, G=glutarate and A=adipate; α -pic= α -picoline, moph=morpholine; d=decomposed.

Based on theoretical values of molecular weights.